

Simulation of Iodine-Sulfur Cycle Hydrogen Production System Driven by VHTR with Jacobian-Split Newton-Krylov Method

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ABSTRACT

VHTR (Very High-Temperature Reactor) can reach an outlet temperature as high as 950 °C or even higher. The Iodine–Sulfur (IS) cycle is a thermochemical process for water splitting to product hydrogen with a theoretical efficiency of nearly 50%. Through cascaded heat utilization, a VHTR serves as an ideal heat source for the IS cycle, while its low-temperature heat can be used for electricity generation and other process heat, thereby achieving high overall energy and exergy efficiencies. In this work, a numerical model of a VHTR-driven IS cycle hydrogen production system is developed to investigate the complex coupling behavior within the system. The strong interactions among the various circuits make the system highly non-linear and challenging to be solved efficiently. The Jacobian-Split Newton–Krylov (JSNK) method, a new variant of Newton-Krylov method, is used for analyzing transient features of the integrated system. The transient response of the coupled system is analyzed under a scenario of reduced primary coolant flow rate. Two modeling approaches are compared: (i) a simultaneous simulation of the multi-circuit system, and (ii) a decoupled simulation under fixed boundary conditions. The pronounced discrepancies between the results yielded by two approaches underscore the intricate interdependence among the reactor primary circuit, the IS cycle, and the power generation system. These findings highlight the necessity and advantages of simulating the integrated system simultaneously with advanced algorithms such as JSNK.

Keywords: VHTR; IS cycle; Coupling; Newton-Krylov method

1. INTRODUCTION

Very High-Temperature Reactor (VHTR) is one of the Generation IV advanced reactor types, known for its exceptionally high outlet temperature. The outlet temperature of VHTR can reach as high as 950 °C or even higher, which is capable of providing high-quality heat for hybrid energy usage. Thermochemical cycle is one of the main hydrogen production methods and it requires heat input to accomplish water splitting by multi-step chemical reactions. Iodine-Sulfur (IS) cycle is a promising thermo-chemical method with theoretical efficiency of nearly 50% [1]. Moreover, it enables closed-loop reuse of all chemical components and promotes sustainability through zero-carbon emissions.

Integrating VHTR as the heat source to drive the IS cycle, while harnessing its rest heat for electricity generation and process heat, represent an ideal strategy to fully exploit the reactor's potential [2][3]. This integrated configuration is hereafter referred to as the Nuclear-Hydrogen system. It supplies heat of different quality to different application sites by energy cascade usage, thereby achieving high energy and exergy efficiency. However, it is a challenging work to simulate its features. On the one hand, the Nuclear-Hydrogen system has complex multi-physics and multi-circuit coupling phenomena. Traditional coupling solution method such as Picard iteration may be unable to accomplish calculation. Newton-Krylov method has advantages in numerical stability and convergence rate when solving the large-scale non-linear system by updating all variables simultaneously, which has been verified in

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previous studies in nuclear engineering [4][5]. On the other hand, the components in IS cycle are highly complex and distinct from the neutronic and thermal-hydraulic processes in nuclear circuits, posing significant challenges for the modeling. Studies performed by Brown [6][7] simulated the IS cycle hydrogen production driven by VHTR with a simplified model of chemical processes, leading to behaviors that differ significantly from those of the actual equipment. In these work, sub-systems such as the primary circuit in reactor side and the IS cycle are solved iteratively through a user-developed interface for data exchange, so the convergence rate is limited, even the convergence cannot be ensured.

In this work, a high-fidelity model of a VHTR-driven IS cycle hydrogen production system is established. This system is solved with the Jacobian-Split Newton-Krylov (JSNK) method, an innovative variant of Newton-Krylov method. The transient behavior of the coupled system is investigated under a scenario of reduced primary coolant flow rate. Two modeling approaches are compared: the first employs a simultaneous solution for the integrated Nuclear-Hydrogen system, where parameters for both the primary circuit and the IS cycle are updated concurrently. In contrast, the second approach decouples the sub-systems by using fixed boundary conditions, thereby neglecting the thermal-load feedback from both sides. The results calculated by these two approaches are used for investigating coupling phenomena within the Nuclear-Hydrogen system and evaluating the necessity of simultaneous solution of the strongly non-linear system.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the numerical model of the coupled system and algorithm of JSNK. Section 3 discusses the coupling phenomena within the Nuclear-Hydrogen system. Finally, Section 4 presents the conclusion.

2. NUMERICAL MODEL AND SOLUTION METHOD

Figure 1. Connection relationship among circuits of the Nuclear-Hydrogen system

2.1. Numerical Model of Nuclear-Hydrogen System

The Nuclear-Hydrogen system consists of four circuits: the primary circuit, the intermediate helium circuit, the IS cycle circuit, and the simplified power generation circuit. The connection relationship among circuits and the operating conditions are shown in Figure 1. A simplified 2-D homogeneous pebble-bed VHTR in the R-Z coordinate [5] with outlet temperature of nearly 950 °C is chosen as the heat source, and the two-group diffusion equation is used to calculate the neutron flux distribution. The primary [8], intermediate helium, secondary, and IS cycle circuits are established using a 1-D network model. The intermediate helium circuit is used for transferring heat from the primary circuit to the IS cycle circuit via an intermediate heat exchanger (IHX) and isolating them for safety. After exchanging heat with the intermediate circuit, the helium in primary circuit then flows through a steam generator (SG) to generate high-temperature steam in its secondary side to drive the secondary circuit and then flows into the core. The numbering in Figure 1 corresponds to key locations within the system:

the reactor core outlet (1) and inlet (3); the hot-side tube outlet (2) and cold-side tube inlet (4) and outlet (5) of IHX 1; and the hot-side tube outlet of IHX 2 (6).

The IS cycle is a three-step water-splitting process consisting of the reactions shown in Eqs. (1)–(3), namely the Bunsen reaction, the sulfuric acid (SA) decomposition reaction, and the hydroiodic acid (HI) decomposition reaction, respectively. Among these reactions, the Bunsen reaction is exothermic, while the left two decomposition reactions are endothermic, taking place at temperatures of 830–900 °C and 300–450 °C, respectively [9].

Figure 2 is the model of IS cycle in the Nuclear-Hydrogen system with two IHXs connected with the intermediate helium circuit. The whole process keeps consistent with the lab-scale closed IS cycle process in INET, Tsinghua University [10]. Within the IS cycle, only the two decomposition reactions necessitate high-quality heat supplied by the VHTR. Other processes—including purification, distillation, and preheating—require only low-quality heat provided by steam extraction from the secondary circuit turbines. For simplification, it is assumed that this low-quality heat is sourced from a dedicated external steam supply characterized by a constant temperature and mass flow.

Figure 2. Simulation model of IS cycle

The IS hydrogen production system involves multiple industrial processes to accomplish production of hydrogen and oxygen. At the outlet of the Bunsen reactor, the sulfuric acid solution and hydroiodic acid solution are mixed, which is unfavorable for the subsequent decomposition reactions. Therefore, the liquid-liquid separator (marked as 301 in Figure 2) is used for separating the light phase (primarily sulfuric acid) and the heavy phase (mainly hydroiodic acid solution mixed with iodine, referred to as the HIx solution) through natural stratification. Because both separated phases contain impurities, purification units (204 and 205) are required. In both the SA purifier and HI purifier, the reverse Bunsen reaction, shown in Eq. (4), occurs to remove impurities.

After purification, the dilute reactant streams must be concentrated to achieve higher conversion rates in the downstream reactors, making the concentration processes essential. The dilute sulfuric acid solution in the light phase is concentrated in distillation column 401, where a product with a concentration above 90% is withdrawn from the bottom and sent to the SA reactor for decomposition. For the heavy phase, the HIx mixture exhibits pseudo-azeotropic behavior, meaning its components are difficult to separate or concentrate using conventional distillation. Electro-electrodialysis (EED) (marked as 901) is employed to increase the HI concentration in the catholyte, allowing the cathode stream to be more efficiently separated and concentrated in the subsequent HI distillation (402) [10]. The concentrated HI solution withdrawn from the top of the HI distillation column is then fed to the

HI reactor 203, where it decomposes to produce I_2 and H_2 . The decomposition products of SA and HI can be fed back to the Bunsen reaction, forming a closed-loop process.

The solution vector for the IS cycle is defined in Eq. (5), It comprises fluid temperature (T), the mole fraction of species i (M_{Fi}), the total mole holdup (M_R) and pressure P in a component, the flow rate at the component boundaries (\dot{m}), and the heat duty transferred through IHXs (Q). Seven distinct species are involved in the IS cycle, namely $H_2O, I_2, SO_2, H_2SO_4, HI, O_2, H_2$. To represent the chemical composition, six independent mole fractions are employed as variables for species $i = I_2, SO_2, H_2SO_4, HI, O_2, H_2$, while the mole fraction of water is determined via Eq. (6), to satisfy the mass conservation constraint. In this work, T, M_{Fi}, M_R and P are categorized as “volume variables”, which are defined within all components, including the chemical reactor, piping, separators; \dot{m} is defined as a “node variable”; Q is a “heater variable” associated with specific heat-transfer units.

$$\mathbf{x}_{IS} = \{T, M_{Fi}, M_R, P, \dot{m}, Q\} \quad (5)$$

$$M_{FH_2O} = 1 - \sum_i M_{Fi} \quad (6)$$

The conservation equations are formulated in residual forms. The conservation of total molar holdup, individual species mole numbers, and energy within each component are defined by Eqs. (7)–(9), respectively.

$$\mathbf{F}(M_R) = \frac{\partial M_R}{\partial t} - \left(\sum \dot{m}_{in,j} - \sum \dot{m}_{out,j} + \dot{M}_{chem} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{F}(M_{Fi}) = \frac{\partial (M_R * M_{Fi})}{\partial t} - \left(\sum \dot{m}_{in,j} M_{F_{in,i,j}} - \sum \dot{m}_{out,j} M_{F_{out,i,j}} + \dot{M}_{chem,i} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{F}(T) = \frac{\partial (\sum M_{R_i} h_i(T))}{\partial t} - \left(\sum \dot{m}_{in,j} h_{j,in} - \sum \dot{m}_{out,j} h_j + q_{chem} \cdot F_a + Q \right) \quad (9)$$

Where, $\dot{m}_{in,j}$ and $\dot{m}_{out,j}$ denote the flow rates of the j^{th} inlet and outlet; $\dot{M}_{chem,i}$ and \dot{M}_{chem} represent the molar production/consumption rates for species i and the total mixture due to chemical reactions; $M_{F_{in,i,j}}$ and $M_{F_{out,i,j}}$ are the mole fractions of species i in the j^{th} inlet and outlet streams; $h_{j,in}$ is the molar enthalpy of the j^{th} inlet mixture, which is a mixture-averaged property determined by the local temperature and pressure; F_a is the chemical reaction rate, governed by reactant concentrations and temperature; q_{chem} is the chemical heat originating from each mole reaction. Furthermore, the mole fraction and temperature of outlet flow are assumed equal to those in the component.

The pressure in a component is assumed to be fixed, while the flow velocity in connecting pipes are decided by pumps. Residual functions for P and \dot{m} are shown in Eq. (10) and (11).

$$\mathbf{F}(P) = P - P_{set} \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{F}(\dot{m}) = \dot{m} - \dot{m}_{set} \quad (11)$$

The residual function of the IHX model is formulated by Eq. (12), where ΔT represents the mean temperature difference cross the heat exchanger, while K and A_{eff} denote the effective heat transfer coefficient and area, respectively.

$$\mathbf{F}(Q) = Q_{IHX} - K \cdot A_{eff} \cdot \Delta T \quad (12)$$

2.2. Efficient Simultaneous Solution Using the JSNK Method

By integrating the governing equations of all circuits, a large-scale nonlinear equation set in the form of $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ is obtained. Newton-Krylov method uses a Krylov subspace method to solve the large-scale Newton linear equations. When solving with the JSNK method, all variables are updated simultaneously, enabling a super-linear convergence rate. The key concept of JSNK method is splitting

the matrix–vector product computation into two parts: the sparse part explicitly computes the Jacobian via finite difference to serve as the preconditioner for capturing strong coupling, and then multiplies it by a vector; while the dense part evaluates the matrix–vector product with a Jacobian-free technique, as shown in Eq. (13). In Eq. (13), \mathbf{x} is the solution vector, $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x})$ is the Jacobian matrix, $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})$ is the residual function of the coupled system, ε is a small perturbation on the solution.

$$\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{J}_S(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{v} + \frac{\mathbf{F}_D(\mathbf{x} + \varepsilon \mathbf{v}) - \mathbf{F}_D(\mathbf{x})}{\varepsilon}, \mathbf{J}_S(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{F}_S(\mathbf{x} + \varepsilon) - \mathbf{F}_S(\mathbf{x})}{\varepsilon} \quad (13)$$

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. Characteristic of Coupling Phenomenon

The simulation is performed using C++. Figure 3(a) is a schematic of coupling logic within the Nuclear-Hydrogen system, where the circuits are interconnected via several IHXs, including the SG. This figure demonstrates that the heat duty of IHXs impacts the physical properties of the fluid, such as enthalpy and viscosity; conversely, the altered fluid state influences the heat power transferred back through IHXs. Additionally, for IHX 2 and IHX 3, the heat duty significantly impacts the chemical reactions within the IS cycle due to temperature-dependent kinetics. Figure 3(b) illustrates the non-zero pattern of the Jacobian matrix, where the elements reflect the coupling relationships among parameters. The system contains a total of 6,020 unknowns: the first 4,625 correspond to the reactor core variables, the next 41 are defined in the primary circuit, followed by 600 for the SG, 103 for the secondary circuit, and the final 651 variables associated with the IS cycle and the intermediate helium circuit.

Figure 3. Coupling phenomenon of the Nuclear-Hydrogen system

The diagonal blocks of the Jacobian matrix represent the internal coupling within individual zones, whereas the off-diagonal blocks, highlighted by red dashed boxes, reflect the inter-circuit or inter-zone coupling relationships. For instance, the IS cycle and the primary circuit are linked through IHX 1, as shown in Figure 1. This interaction arises from the heat duty of IHX 1, which is determined by the temperature gradient between the helium of primary-side and the fluid within the intermediate helium circuit. This structured sparsity of the Jacobian matrix is explicitly utilized in the JSNK solver to optimize the preconditioning process and accelerate convergence.

3.2. Results under Steady State

In steady state, the integrated system maintains stable hydrogen production and electricity generation rate. JSNK method converges after 11 Newton steps and 988 GMRES steps in total. Significant parameters under steady state are listed in Table I.

Table I. Steady parameters of the poly-generation system.

Parameter	Value
Reactor thermal power	250 WM
k_{eff}	0.996639
Helium mass velocity in primary circuit	68.57kg/s
T_1	951.71 °C
T_2	748.68 °C
T_3	250.24 °C
T_4	520.00 °C
T_5	880.85 °C
T_6	550.74 °C
Heat duty of IS cycle	392.0 kJ/mol – H ₂
Temperature of SA reactor	851.32 °C
Temperature of HI reactor	453.52 °C

3.3. Results Comparison of Two Approaches

Figure 4. Comparison of temperatures and powers calculated by two approaches

A transient scenario is simulated to analyze the system's response to a reduction in the primary coolant flow rate from 68.57 kg/s to 48.57 kg/s over a 50-second interval; subsequently, the flow rate is maintained at 48.57 kg/s for the remaining 450 seconds to observe the subsequent evolution of the system's parameters. Two modeling approaches are compared: Approach 1 performs a simultaneous solution for the integrated system, enabling bidirectional coupling among circuits. Approach 2 decouples the Nuclear-Hydrogen system into two distinct modules: the primary/secondary circuit group and the IS cycle part. Specifically, the transient response is simulated under fixed boundary conditions, where the core outlet temperature is prescribed as a constant. Meanwhile, the heat duty of the IS cycle, determined by the second module, is applied as the cold-side heat load of IHX 1 in the first

module. This comparison aims to reveal the calculation deviations arising from decoupling the system and provide a baseline to assess how crucial the coupling among circuits is for capturing the true transient characteristic. The comparison of temperatures and heat powers of different components calculated by two approaches is shown in Figure 4, where the subscripts “cp” and “dcp” denote the parameters for Approach 1 and Approach 2, respectively.

Figure 4(a) illustrates the contrasting treatments of core outlet temperature between the two approaches. The reduction in flow rate introduces negative reactivity into the reactor, causing a decline in core power, as shown in Figure 4(d); this trend is consistently predicted by both approaches. However, the core experiences degraded cooling due to the reduced coolant flow, leading to a temperature rise in the fuel pebbles and, consequently, a higher coolant outlet temperature (T_{out}). Although the active transient setting finishes at 50 s, the temperatures of the reactor core and the outlet coolant continue to rise due to thermal inertia. For Approach 1, the core outlet temperature reaches its peak approximately 80 s after the initiation of the transient, whereas in Approach 2, this parameter is held constant at its initial steady-state value throughout the entire transient process. The failure of Approach 2 to capture this temperature peak demonstrates the limitation of decoupled models in predicting the thermal feedback between the core and downstream components. A decrease in core power leads to a lower core outlet temperature, which in turn tends to increase the core power. The changes of the coolant temperature and reactor thermal power shown by Figure 4(a) and 4(d) reflect the negative feedback mechanism in the reactor. The power deviation is defined as the result of Approach 1 minus that of Approach 2. Since the coolant temperature predicted by Approach 1 is higher than that of Approach 2, the reactor core power in Approach 1 is slightly lower.

Under a reduced mass flow rate, the reactor thermal power must be extracted through a larger coolant temperature rise across the core; a lower core inlet temperature (T_{in}) is consequently observed in Figure 4(a). Due to the significant heat capacity of the reactor core, the discrepancy in core outlet temperature between the two approaches remains marginal, less than 1.5 °C. As a result, the core inlet temperatures predicted by both approaches are in close agreement. The reduced primary coolant flow rate diminishes the heat transfer coefficient between the hot gas and the IHX 1 tube walls, leading to a decrease in the IHX 1 heat duty (Q_{IHX1} in Figure 4(e)). After 50 s, while the primary mass flow rate is maintained constant, the IHX 1 tube temperature rises due to the continuous flow of high-temperature coolant, subsequently increasing Q_{IHX1} . Given the substantial heat capacity of the solid tubes, Q_{IHX1} exhibits minimal fluctuations, even as the core outlet temperature varies.

The heat duty of IS cycle (Q_{IS} in Figure 4(f)) represents the heat power transferred from the hot fluid to the cold fluid in the intermediate helium circuit, which is directly dependent on Q_{IHX1} . Consequently, the trend observed in Figure 4(f) is consistent with that in Figure 4(e). The values of Q_{IHX1} and Q_{IS} calculated by Approach 1 are consistently higher than those of Approach 2, because of the higher average temperature of the primary coolant. The reduction in Q_{IS} leads to a lower temperature level in the intermediate helium circuit, including the cold-side outlet temperature of IHX 1 (T_5 in Figure 4(b)). After 50 s, although the IS cycle heat duty increases again and the cold-side temperature rise of IHX 1 is higher, the overall temperature level of the intermediate helium circuit is still lower; thus, T_5 continues to decrease before becoming stable. In the IS cycle, the temperatures of the chemical reactors (the SA and HI reactors) follow the temperature levels of the hot helium in the intermediate circuit, as shown in Figure 4(c). The temperature difference on the hot side of IHX 1 increases during the 50-second flow reduction, leading to a decrease in T_2 . Once the primary flow rate is fixed, T_2 decreases further as more heat is transferred to the cold side of IHX 1.

The discrepancies of fluid temperatures and component powers predicted by the two approaches underscore the necessity of a simultaneous simulation of the integrated system. Specifically, the higher temperatures predicted by Approach 1 introduce stronger negative reactivity feedback compared to Approach 2. From a safety perspective, these results suggest that a decoupled boundary may underestimate the complexity of the transient response and yield lower temperature predictions, potentially masking the actual high-temperature risks to which components are exposed.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A VHTR-driven IS cycle hydrogen production system represents a promising strategy for hybrid utilization of nuclear energy, enabling large-scale hydrogen and power generation. In this study, a

computational model of the Nuclear-Hydrogen system is established and solved with the JSNK method to investigate the transient behaviors of the integrated system. Numerical results demonstrate intensive thermal coupling among the various circuits, where changes of parameters in one circuit/component will trigger dynamic responses for the whole system. Furthermore, due to the system's complexity and strong non-linearities, it is necessary to employ a simultaneous approach that accounts for thermal feedback among circuits and updates all parameters concurrently. The decoupled approach using fixed boundary conditions introduces calculation deviations. This work demonstrates the necessity of fully coupled simulations for nuclear hydrogen production systems, and highlights the excellent stability and efficiency of the Jacobian-Split Newton-Krylov (JSNK) method. This paper only employs a simplified secondary circuit model with basic heat exchange nodes. Future research will focus on developing a refined secondary circuit model that considers individual components, incorporating steam extraction from the turbine to the IS cycle, and establishing a high-fidelity distillation model for the IS cycle accounting for multi-component phase equilibrium, thereby further improving the simulation and analysis capability

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